

Type J.A.	Origin	latitude	longitude	SH US	SH OS	SH I	SH not-stratified	TW US	TW MS	TW OS	TW not-stratified	Ho IA	Si A	Si B	Si not-stratified
001	Jura Mounains, undefined							371	471	734	60	74	15	17	1
009	Radiolarites, undefined											6			
10	Belgium-Netherlands	50.796	5.744			2									
108	Albeuve-Neirivue	46.520	7.044		2			1	2	2					
109	Lausen-Cholholz	47.457	7.759					3	6	2					
112	Paron	48.175	3.218		3	4		1	1	12					
113	Arces-Dilo/Charmes	48.082	3.562		1			2	2	7	2				
114	Alle-Les Aiges, Noir-Bois, Pré-au-Prince	47.417	7.124		2										
119	Poncin/Saint-Alban	46.094	5.408	1	5	1		3	13	16	1				
123	o.u., Jura sud?	46.6	6.3						1						
126	o.u., Meuse?	48.8	5.5							1					
129	Veaux/Combe de Launier	44.170	5.162		6			4	4	3					
130	Poland Chocolate Flint	50.9	21.6							1					
135	Bendorf-Kohlberg	47.476	7.280		2										
139	Meusnes	47.246	1.467	1		2			1	4					
141	Ferrara di Monte Baldo	45.698	10.87									1			1
142	Pleigne-Löwenburg	47.438	7.327	1	4			1	1			3			
143	Crépy-en-Valois	49.247	2.861					5	18	16	2				
149	Origny-Sainte-Benoîte	49.812	3.538							2					
153	Abensberg/Arnhofen	48.835	11.87							2					
156	Châteauneuf-les-Martigues	43.380	5.157						8						
157	Cerro Veronese (Lessini)	45.575	11.03												2
159	Kleinkems-Isteiner Klotz	47.677	7.529			1									
167	Treschenu-Creyers/Pellebit	44.741	5.520			2									
169	Arzo	45.876	8.548					2	4	1					
174	Grömitz/ Suxdorf	54.165	10.92						1						
177	Herblingen-Grüthalde/Lohn-Oberholz	47.730	8.659									27			
180	Vordingberg/Mon	54.947	12.30			1									
184	Baiersdorf	48.962	11.74												2
186	Coizard	48.838	3.863			1				1					
187	Cmielow	50.894	21.52			3			2						
201	Chézery-la-Rivière; Bellegarde-Seysssel	46.236	5.891						1						
205	Préalpes fribourgeoises	46.677	7.531			2			1		1				
207	Mont-les-Etrelles	47.454	5.867		2			4	14	144	1				
212	Laval St Roman	44.298	4.505			47			2	20					
221	outcrop unknown									2					
229	Rijkholt-Sint-Geertruid	50.796	5.744							2		2			
232	Véron/Puits-Bottin	48.127	3.330							3					
233	Romigny-Lhéry	49.201	3.764									1			
250	o.u., Italie nord Alps?	45.698-46.317	10.875-11.140							1					
252	Sanilhac/La Lauzas	44.530	4.258					2	8	29	3				
259	Cles/ Val di Non	46.390	11.079												1
261	Mellecey-Fôret de Marlou	46.819	4.755			7				3	1				
262	Forcalquier-Vallée du Largue	43.970	5.766					1	1						
271	«Randenregion»; Bütttenhardt	47.754	8.637									25	36	12	
282	Monte Sant'Angelo/ Gargano	41.931	15.99				1		1			1			2
286	Sondersdorf/ Lindenfeld	47.476	7.343					5	1	4					
291	Herblingen/ Rosenhalde	47.726	8.657											5	
293	o.u., Netherlands	50.7	5.7			12									
305	Diemtigen-Stockhorn 1 (Simmental)	46.677	7.531					1	2						
313	Liel-Schneckenberg	47.733	7.595					1		2	1	1			
314	Cornol/Sous les Roches 2	47.733	7.595		2										
330	Lains	46.376	5.487			1									
334	Vassieux-en-Vercors	44.918	5.372						3						
337	Ambel 5 (Vercours)	44.893	5.317			1									
340	Avignon-les-St-Claude	46.392	5.840							1					
346	Mühlhausen-Ehingen	47.830	8.812									296	3	1	1
349	Degerfelden	47.573	7.742			2				6					
357	Rougemont	46.517	7.230			1									
359	Oberiberg; moraines nord	47.025	8.757			1			4						
366	Thayngen, face au Kesslerloch	47.744	8.694									38		9	1
371	Bresse	47.204	5.541								1				
373	Pellebit	44.741	5.520												
375	Wittlingen (Bad Urach)	48.461	9.452									1			
388	Grane/Pierre Sanglante	44.683	4.891					1							
390	St. Euphémie-sur-Ouvéze	44.297	5.380							1					
401	Saint-Blaise, Champs Magnins	47.014	6.972	2	1			1	1	13					
404	Le Paquier, route des Bugnenets	47.115	7.001						1						
413	Solérieux-Villesèque	443404	4.818					1	2	5					
414	Crotenay	46.752	5.795							4	1				
415	Cortébert-Pierrefeu	47.153	7.114					9	6	12					
419	Dossenbach-Frickstalten, Dinkelberg	47.621	7.859							3	1				
420	Balme de Thuy	45.902	6.285							3					
421	Yverdon-Moulin Cousseau	46.781	6.609						4	3					
422	Pontarlier/Les Etraches	46.930	6.413			1									
427	Lengnau-Vorberg	47.181	7.357			8									
440	Châteauneuf-du-Pape	44.072	4.797							1					
504	Lampenberg-Stälzler	47.419	7.738					1	2	1					
515	Canton Baselland	47.439	7.687					1		3					
520	Dordogne	44.936	1.012							1					
616	Rougemont	46.502	7.198							1	1				
620	Breitachtal (Tiefenbach)	47.415	10.253									2			
632	Napf; moraines north	47.187	7.997						1	1			2		
633	Chur, disappeared; Rhine pebbles	46.849	9.529			1							2		
646	Bellvavista (Monte Generoso)	45.887	8.986					1							
652	Möhlín; Beinwil, Lampenberg	47.570	7.830					1	1	1					
654	Kleinwalsertal Oberstorf	47.401	10.302						3			1			
655	Alps ; moraines					1									
802	Paron	48.175	3.218							1					
812	Randen	47.758	8.581									16			
1212	Saint-Brisson sur Loire - La Pelaude	47.649	2.699					1	3	16	1				
1214	BP nord, cf ouest des Marais de St-Gond	48.838	3.863					1	2						
1215	Vervo/ Casanova	46.317	11.140						2						
1216	Sümeg	46.976	17.328						1	2					
1217	Oberlarg	48.920	2.755							30	2				
1218	Schienerberg	47.691	8.937									1			
1234	not yet found					12									
2328	Itza	51.147	21.239							2					
3403	Guntmadingen/ Lieberstobel (=146/002-H)	47.823	10.443					1							
3413	Mäd/ Sás Patak HerzegEöves	48.530	20.866					7	21	39	2				
2317	Mäd/ Sás Patak HerzegEöves	48.530	20.866		1			1	29	21	1				
102	Chalchofen Olten	47.332	7.890									4			
101/102/311	Olten Region (macroscopically determined)	47.332	7.890	46	132	204	1	3	7	12					
146/002	Otelfingen-Lägern	47.479	8.387	19	44	142	1	4	11	19		10			
236, 243, 2329	outcrop unknown							2	2	49					
436, HW 20	Moraines Ulm bis Engen	47.853	8.800									22	22	37	
HW 15	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									3			
HW 15-e	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									1			
HW 8	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									84			
HW 8b-e	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									2			
HW 9	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									103			
HW 9-e	o.u., Randen region	47.754	8.637									7			
rock crystal	Alps					6		19	60	40	1	?	2		
0	not determinable			2	12	37		8	34	41	7	15	6	2	4
Total				72	219	503	3	470	766	1347	89	747	88	85	13